

Effect of Work Family Conflict and Job Satisfaction on Quality of Work Life

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This study attempted to investigate the effect of work family conflict and job satisfaction on quality of work life. Data was obtained from two hundred (200) respondents, of which one hundred and eighty-nine was found valid for analysis. The respondent used consists of (100) female workers and (89) male workers both in the public and private sectors, respondents reside and work in Adom Ekiti. Three instruments were used in this study to measure work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life. Three hypotheses were tested. This study shows that there is a significant effect of work family conflict and job satisfaction on quality of work life, but there are no significant sex differences in work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life.

Key words: Quality of work life, Job satisfaction, Work – family conflict, Organization

INTRODUCTION

A high quality of work life is essential for organizations to continue to attract and retain employees. Sometimes abbreviated QWL, quality of work life is quick phrase that encompasses a lot, because it refers to the thing an employer does that adds to the lives of employees. Those “things” are some combination of benefits explicit and implied, tangible and intangible that make somewhere good place to work and another a bad place to work. In an organization, a high level of quality of work life is necessary to continue to attract and retain employees. Retina and Ismay (2006), reviewed different research about meanings and constructions of quality of work life and designated that quality of work life is a multidimensional construct and is made of several interrelated factors. Quality of work life is a set of principles which holds that people are the most important resource in the organization as they are trustworthy, responsible and capable of making valuable contribution and they should be treated with dignity and respect (Straw and Heckscher, 1984). Quality of work life entails the design of work systems that enhance the working life experiences of organizational members, thereby improving commitment to and motivation for achieving organizational goals.

Organizations are continuously looking for new ways of doing business to meet the challenges of today’s dynamic business environment. Given the amount of time and energy people expend at the workplace, it is important for employees to be satisfied with their life at work. Glass & Finley, (2002), Van der Lippe, (2007) argued that time pressure is a serious problem in today’s workforce, with ever-increasing numbers of workers bearing major responsibilities at home and meeting higher job expectations and heavier demands at work. A mismatch between family and work roles can be disadvantageous for both employees and employers. In fact, as early as 1960’s researchers began to study and connect the dots between work and family. Numerous researchers such as Greenhaus and Powell, (2006), Owolabi and Babalola (2014) demonstrate that what happened in the workplace has significant impact on individuals and their families. Researchers have shown that the combination of a fluctuating work environment with competing job and family

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A review of literature according to Chandranshu (2012) shows that there are twelve important factors that enhance the quality of employee work life especially when the management of an organization works towards the development of organization's most valuable assets (employees). The factors include the following: effective and efficient communication system, opportunity for career development and personal growth, organizational committed and emotional supportive supervisor, flexible work arrangement that permit employee to have time for personal issues, a responsive family culture, a highly design employee motivation system, supportive organizational climate, organizational support system, job satisfaction; adequate rewards and benefits system and compensation.

Job Satisfaction

Research indicates that employee satisfaction is important to an organization's success. Job satisfaction is a widely studied construct in organizational behavior as it influences other organizational variables like productivity, turnover and absenteeism. Atchison (1999) states that many organizations are spending much time on employee satisfaction initiatives to reduce turnover, improve productivity and help organizations succeed. Hoole and Vermeulen (2003) maintain that the popularity of this field of study is also due to its relevance to the physical and mental well-being of employees. Furthermore, Robbins (2005) postulates that managers have a humanistic responsibility to provide employees with jobs that are challenging, rewarding and satisfying. According to Alavi and Khairpur (2003), there are at least three reasons why managers must focus on the job satisfaction of their employees.

- Evidence suggests that unsatisfied individuals leave organizations.
- Satisfied employees are in better health and have longer life expectancy. Connolly and Myers (2003) further maintain that a lack of job satisfaction has been associated with symptoms like anxiety, depression and poor physical and psychological health, which have concomitant consequences for absenteeism and commitment.
- Job satisfaction in the workplace also affects individuals' private lives, which in turn influences absenteeism and other important work-related attitudes and behavior.

Rhodes & Steers (1990) list seven factors related to the job situation that could lead to increased job satisfaction, namely, job scope, job level, role stress, size of the work group, style of the leader, coworker relations and the opportunity for advancement. Job satisfaction is a complex variable and is influenced by factors of the job environment as well as dispositional characteristics of an individual. These factors have been arranged according to two dimensions, namely, extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Buiten Dach & De Witte 2005). The extrinsic factors include things like pay, promotion opportunities, coworkers, supervision and recognition. Intrinsic factors include personality, education, intelligence and abilities, age and marital status (Mullins, 1999). Extrinsic sources of job satisfaction are determined by conditions that are beyond the control of the employee (Atchison, 1999). The following have been discovered to affect job satisfaction, namely, pay, the job itself, promotion opportunities, supervision, coworkers, working conditions and the issue of fairness

Work family conflict

Managing the conflict between family and work obligations is an important issue. The demands of family and work pose critical challenges to individuals, researchers, and organizations. In Malaysia, the percentage of women in tertiary education and, consequently, in professional roles has been rising steadily. In 1990, 45.7% of women were

in tertiary education (Department of Statistics, Malaysia 1992) compared with 38.6% in 1980 (Department of Statistics, Malaysia 1983). Of the economically active population, 10.7% of women were in professional, technical and related occupations in 1992 (Department of Statistics, Malaysia 1994) compared with 4.8% in 1970 (Department of Statistics, Malaysia 1972). With these changing demographics, women must deal with job related demands which place limits on the performance of their family role. This trend results in work family conflict as women try to cope with conflicting demands of work and the family (Aminah 1995). In Nigeria, men have traditionally played the role of breadwinner in the family while the women stay back to take care of the home front with little or no formal job, but things have change drastically with more women become career person just like their husband. To Aryee (1999), the increased participation of married women in the labor force in the US and other industrialized countries has led to a growing realization that the work and family domains are highly interdependent. He observes that adults in dual earner and single parent households must constantly strive to balance work and family requirements.

In the last few decades, scholars studying work family conflict have accumulated ample evidence that work family conflict is an important and pervasive phenomenon, with unfavorable consequences, such as stress (Allen 2000), job dissatisfaction (Kosek & Ozeki, 1998), lowered performance and commitment, and turnover (Kosek & Ozeki, 1999). Consequently, prevention of work family conflict is becoming an increasingly pressing problem for companies. In this work the aim is to investigate how work family conflict and job satisfaction affect quality of work life.

Hypothesis to be tested

1. There will be a significant effect of work family conflict on quality of work life.
2. There will be a significant effect of job satisfaction on quality of work life.
3. There will be a significant effect of sex on work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life.

METHODS

Research design

Survey research using the independent group design was used for the study. This was achieved through the administration of a carefully controlled questionnaire.

Participants

The sample used in this study comprises one hundred and eighty-nine (189) participants, ninety Zone (91) from public sector and ninety-eight (98) from private sector. The sample population is made up of one hundred female (100) and eighty-nine (89) males. Workers in the public sectors include teachers, medical doctors' nurses and also workers in private sector including private school teachers, medical doctors and nurses of private hospitals, they are all residents and working in Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State.

Instruments

Three main psychological constructs were measured using self-report instruments. Questionnaire with section AZD was administered to participants. Section A of the questionnaire contains demographic information of the participants. Questions relating to occupation respondents were asked to specify their occupation as either working in the public sector or private sector, respondents were also asked to indicate their gender, age and educational qualification.

Section B contains an instrument used for measuring quality of work life called

The Leiden Quality of Work life Scale developed by Margot and Stan (1999). The Leiden Quality of Work Life Scale was constructed to assess work characteristics from two influential occupational stress models, the Job Demand Control Support model (Johnson & Hall, 1988; Johnson, 1989; Karasek & Theorell, 1990) and the Michigan model (Caplan, Cobb, French, Van Harrison & Pineau, 1975). It measures 12 work characteristics, namely, skill discretion, decision authority, task control, work and time pressure, role ambiguity, physical exertion, hazardous exposure, job insecurity, lack of meaningfulness, social support from supervisors and social support from coworkers and the outcome variable of job satisfaction.

Section C contains an instrument for measuring work and family conflict called Work Family Conflict Scale (WFC). It was designed by Netemeyer, Boles and McMurrian (1996) to measure the relationship between work and family conflict and family and work conflict among individuals in working population. In terms of reliability, Chung et al. (2004) reported coefficient alphas ranging from .87 to .91 for country-of-origin subscale and .76 to .81 for European American subscale. Test-retest reliability for the two subscales were reported to be

.89 and .78 respectively. Reliability data for the domain subscales ranged from .76 to .87 for language, .65 to .71 for food consumption, .67 to .89 for cultural knowledge, and .74 to .79 for cultural identity for the acculturation and enculturation measures. According to Netemeyer et al. (1996), the internal consistencies of both scales are adequate, with alpha estimates ranging from .83 to .89, and an average alpha of .88 for WFC, and of .86 for FWC).

Section D contains job satisfaction scale which was used for measuring the level of satisfaction an individual has as regards his job. The Generic Job Satisfaction Scale was designed by Scott MacDonald and Peter MacIntyre (1997) to measure job satisfaction. The Cronbach's alpha reliability for this scale is ($\alpha = .77$). The diversity of item themes likely reduced the reliability coefficient. However, a diversity of items is consistent with the intent to include the relevant facets of job satisfaction of what was been measured.

The subjects were selected and questionnaires administered at their various workplaces, because there was no special place set aside for this purpose, the difficult items were discussed with the respondents, and they were also informed that the data is for research purposes. Two hundred subjects participated in the study while one hundred and eighty-nine were found valid for analysis.

Method of data analysis

Four hypotheses were tested in this study. Independent test was used in analyzing the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Hypothesis one which states that there will be a significant effect of work family conflict on quality of work life was tested using the independent t test. The result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.1: independent test table showing the effect of work family conflict on quality of work life.

Variable	Level	N	Mean	SD	Def.	t	P
Work Family Conflict	High	102	26.48	4.97	187	4.37	< 0.05
	Low	87	38.07	3.58			

From Table 4.1 above, the result shows that there is a significant effect of work family conflict on quality of work life $t(187) = 4.37, p < .05$. A closer look at the mean score reveals that employees with higher experience of work family conflict have lower level of quality of work life as compared to employees with lower experience of work family conflict.

Hypothesis two which states that there will be a significant effect of job satisfaction on quality of work life was tested using the independent t test. The result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.2: independent test table showing the effect of job satisfaction on quality of work life.

Variable	Level	N	Mean	SD	Def.	t	P
Job satisfaction	High	76	35.97	6.58	187	7.67	< 0.05
	Low	113	163.07	4.58			

From Table 4.2 above, the result shows that there is a significant effect of job satisfaction on quality of work life $t(187) = 7.67, p < .05$. A closer look at the mean score reveals that employees with higher experience of job satisfaction have higher level of quality of work life as compared to employees with lower experience of job satisfaction. Hypothesis three which states that there will be a significant effect of sex on work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life was tested using the independent t test. The result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.3: independent t test table showing the effect of sex on work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life.

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Def.	t	P
Work family conflict	Male	89	25.99	9.17	187	0.19	>.05
	Female	100	26.90	8.86			
Quality of work life	Male	89	161.46	32.29	187	0.82	>.05
	Female	100	164.75	22.69			
Job satisfaction	Male	89	35.98	9.20	187	0.04	>.05
	Female	100	35.92	10.00			

From Table 4.3 above, the results shows that there are no significant sex differences in the perception of work family conflict $t(187) = 0.19, p > .05$, quality of work life $t(187) = 0.82, p > .05$ and job satisfaction $t(187) = 0.04, p > .05$. The hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that there is no significant effect of gender on work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life.

DISCUSSION

Hypothesis one which states that there will be a significant effect of work family conflict on quality of work life was tested using independent t test. The results show there is a significant effect of work family conflict on quality of work life. The hypothesis is therefore confirmed. The result reveals that employees with higher experience of work family conflict have poor quality of work life. This finding corroborates previous research on quality of work life.

In a study conducted by Lococo and Roschelle (1991), they observed that work

related stress and balancing work and nonwork life domains affects quality of work life significantly and should be conceptually considered as determinants of quality of working life. In line with the suggestion by Herriot (1992) that many a time's people find themselves in conflict between family life and work and what they perceive as success in life as compared to what success they get. Family and work are two most important domains of life and balance is crucial. It is observed that because of the conflicting role demands between job and family, and commitment, QWL is inversely proportional to the work conflict, meaning that the higher the work role conflict, the lower will be the quality of family life, and vice versa. Difficulties in meeting demands from the two-settings work family conflict, might be due to the amount of time spend at work (Karstadt, Ingra, & Eriksen, 2003; Van Rijswijk, Bekker, Rutte, & Croon, 2004) or a result traditional sex roles (Lindfors, Berntsson, & Lundberg, 2006).

Given that more women are entering the workforce, it has become imperative to understand how men and women might differ in their job attitudes. This research study tries to observe if gender had any significant effect on work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life. Research report by Bellavia and Frone (2005) showed that men report higher but not statistically significant level of interference than women in two national surveys, while some other researchers found significantly lower level of interference (Grzywacz, Almeida, & McDonald, 2002; Menino, Rubin, & Brayfield, 2005; Winslow, 2005). Further studies showed that WIF occurred more than FIW among male employees due to commitment to work responsibilities in relation to family responsibilities (Eby, et al., 2005; Geurts, Taris, Compeer, Dikkers, van Hooff, & Kinnunen, 2005). Just as studies from Berntsson, Lundberg and Krantz (2006) disclosed that men focused mainly on their work role, which seemed to be resistant to feelings related to conflicting demands. Although, women are not fully exempted with this type of conflict, they however continue to spend more time on childcare and housework, while men have generally increased their contributions and reduced the gap with women as FIW is conversely more related to wellbeing (Bianchi, Robinson, & Milkie, 2006). Given the openness of the economy, political changes, changes in societal values, the balance of job and family obligation has shifted dramatically. According to Frone and Rice (1987), the shifts in family and work domains, individuals must face and adapt to the interzone conflict. Research in this regard has been consistent, different researchers' reports different views on the issue of gender as either having effect or not. A study conducted by Alavi & Khairpur (2003) amongst 310 employees in government organization found no significant effect in job satisfaction among male and female employees. A possible explanation is offered by Tolbert & Moen (1998), who maintains that men and women attach value to different aspects of the job. This therefore makes it a bit difficult to measure difference of gender in work family conflict, job satisfaction and quality of work life.

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